

Thermal analysis of thermo electric generator for waste heat recovery

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ABSTRACT

The thermoelectric generators (TEGs) are used to generate electric power. Thermo electric modules which are used in TEGs are utilized to change the thermal energy into electrical energy and it operates on the basic concept of Seebeck effect. Power generation by Thermo-Electric (TE) materials is an interesting method for the direct translation of thermal energy into electrical energy. This work discovers a method of analysis on the performance of TEGs with different materials for recovering the waste heat and converts it into electric power. For this, an experimental setup for waste heat recovery and energy conversion equipment was designed and fabricated. The TEGs made by Bismuth Telluride (Bi_2Te_3), Lead Telluride (PbTe), and Silicon Germanium (SiGe) are taken for the performance analysis. From these above-mentioned TE materials, the Bismuth Telluride (Bi_2Te_3) has better performance when compared with others within a temperature span that is most appropriate for cooling and heating utilities.

Keywords

Thermo electric generator (TEG), Waste heat recovery (WHR), Lead Telluride (PbTe), Silicon Germanium (SiGe), Bismuth Telluride (Bi_2Te_3)

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I. INTRODUCTION

The machineries which do work or other energy transformation produce heat along with the output power. This heat is termed as waste heat as it is discharged in the environment. This waste heat after being discharged to the environment causes the rise in temperature of the environment. Due to this an adverse effect is created on the environment [1-3]. The heat generation shows that a partial input energy is wasted and not transferred into useful work. Preferably there should be no waste heat but it is not almost likely to transfer all the input energy into work [4, 5]. It can be tough or intricate to improve the effectiveness of any machine directly but the efficiency is indirectly increased if the produced waste heat is utilized for some other purposes [6-9]. Conversion of the heat energy into electric power is a one of the methods to use the waste heat. TEG is a device which can be utilized to transfer heat into electricity and it operates on the concept of Seebeck effect i.e., it converts the change in temperature into electric power [10-12]. The change in temperature is needed at both ends of a TEG to generate a potential difference (voltage). More in temperature difference will create more in the degree of the power generated [13-16]. TEGs are generally made up of different materials like Bismuth Telluride (Bi_2Te_3) alloys, Lead Telluride (PbTe) alloys and Silicon Germanium (SiGe) alloys. The performance of these different material TEGs was analyzed and best one was found.

II. METHODOLOGY

Waste heat is generated in nearly every energy translation process. This waste heat is passed to the atmosphere and has an adverse result on it. Investigations express that practically 33% of the total expended energy is goes as waste heat. Present days it is very much needed to recover and utilize this energy as the fossil fuels are exhausting rapidly. The waste heat can be re-claimed in several ways thereby improving the performance of the processes. TEGs are used for this purpose.

Heaters serve as heating devices and TEGs with a size of 40 mm x 40 mm x 4 mm are used to produce electricity from the change in temperature across its junctions. This experiment was conducted by fixing the TEG between an electrical heaters and water-cooling system. The heat input to the electric heater was changed between 20W and 120 W. The measurement of temperature was carried by thermocouple. TEGs work on the Seebeck's effect principle. TEGs have a several merits than the other electric power generators such as free in pollution, solid state, no maintenance needed, light in weight, noiseless operation and it is a passive device. The heater is connected to a dimmer stat of 600W. The ampere and the voltage is monitored using an ammeter and the voltmeter. The output of the TEG is connected to the voltmeter and the ammeter to measure the output power generated. Now when the electric heater is switched on and at the same time the cooling water is fed through the block. The TEG produces the electric power by the Seebeck's effect. Then three different kinds of TEGs are fixed one by one and the experiment was carried. The work flow is mentioned in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Experimental Setup

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The experiments were carried out for three different TEGs by changing the heat input value from 20W to 120W with a step of 20W raise. During the experiments, the steady state was attained after 5 minutes of continuous running of the heater. The [TABLE I](#) shows the experimental results of the TEGs. An effort has been taken to conserve the heat of heater with TEG and electricity was produced by using TEGs. It was observed that, if there is an increase in the heater input power, there is a rise in temperature difference between hot and cold end of TEGs and then the rate of electricity generation is also increased. The energy conversion efficiency of TEG was determined by utilizing [equation \(1\)](#).

$$\eta_{TEG} = \frac{P_o}{Q_i} \quad \text{----- (1)}$$

Fig. 2 Maximum power generated versus TEG Material

TABLE I
PERFORMANCE OF TEGS

TEG Material	Input Heater Power (Q _i) (W)	Average ΔT (°C)	Maximum Power Generated (P _o) (W)	Conversion Efficiency η _{TEG} (%)
Bi ₂ Te ₃	20	16	0.06	0.30%
	40	28	0.24	0.60%
	60	52	0.52	0.87%
	80	68	0.84	1.05%
	100	85	1.37	1.37%
	120	95	1.72	1.43%
PbTe	20	15	0.05	0.25%
	40	29	0.23	0.58%
	60	50	0.51	0.85%
	80	67	0.84	1.05%
	100	83	1.34	1.34%
	120	95	1.70	1.42%
SiGe	20	15	0.05	0.25%
	40	28	0.23	0.58%
	60	50	0.51	0.85%
	80	66	0.82	1.03%
	100	82	1.32	1.32%
	120	94	1.68	1.40%

Fig. 3 Conversion Efficiency versus TEG Material

As the load on the heater increases the heater consumes more quantity of current to compensate the load, hence heating of more heater results in an increase temperature. High temperature led to elevate the performance of the TEG and produces more electricity. In these three TEGs the Bi₂Te₃ gives better performance when compared with the others. It gives the maximum temperature difference of 95°C, maximum generated power of 1.72 W and the maximum conversion efficiency of 1.43% as shown in [Fig. 2](#).

IV. CONCLUSION

The energy conversion efficiency of the TEGs will be subject to the change in temperature across its junctions. The efficiency of different TEG material was found using the experimental setup and the results are summarized as follows:

- It is found that if the heat input value increases, then the temperature difference increases.
- Due to the increase in temperature difference the power generated and conversion efficiency also increases.
- The Bi₂Te₃ TEG produced maximum power of 1.72W with the conversion efficiency of 1.43% when compared with PbTe and SiGe as shown in the [Fig. 3](#).

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